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Position 28

SAFETY ASSESSMENT OF HERBAL FOOD SUPPLEMENTS: ETHANOL, METHANOL AND BENZENE ASSOCIATED RISK FOR TODDLERS

Sladana Vojvodić¹, Branislava Srđenović Čonić^{1,2}, Ljilja Torović^{1,2,3}

¹*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Center for Medical and Pharmaceutical Investigations and Quality Control, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

³*Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Futoška 121, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia*

E-mail: sladja.vojvodic@uns.ac.rs

Introduction: Liquid herbal food supplements could contain significant levels of ethanol as well as low levels of methanol or other organic solvents used in preparation of herbal extracts. Benzoates, used as preservatives to prolong product's shelf-life, could react with ascorbic acid, which can be naturally present in herbs or added as an active ingredient or antioxidant, and form benzene, known human carcinogen. Ingestion of toxic solvents and/or benzene through consumption of herbal supplements could pose a health risk, especially in early life.

Materials and methods: Liquid herbal food supplements intended for toddlers (n=26) were purchased from pharmacies in Novi Sad (Serbia) and analysed using HSS-GC-MS for the presence of ethanol and methanol, and additionally benzene in eight samples preserved with sodium benzoate. Consequent exposure and associated risk were assessed.

Results: Ethanol was quantified in all but one sample, despite the position of the European Medicinal Agency that herbal products containing ethanol should not be used in children below two years of age. World Health Organization proposed requirement for ethanol content in products intended for children less than six years old (<0.5%) was not met by eight samples. Calculated blood alcohol concentrations exceeded the toxicological levels for eight samples following a single dose, and for one sample in case of accidental poisoning with entire package. Methanol was quantified in 15 samples, in one of them above the Ph.Eur. limit of 0.05%, causing exceedance of permitted daily exposure. Benzene was found in one sample in quantity causing no health concerns according to minimum risk level, hazard quotient, margin of exposure and lifetime cancer risk approaches.

Conclusions: Strict guidelines for ethanol content and labeling should be established, along with raising awareness of professionals and parents, the latter commonly having no suspicion of potentially associated adverse health effects of natural products.

Keywords: herbal supplements, risk assessment, ethanol, methanol, benzene